

D8.3: Dissemination & Communication Materials

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Abstract:

Dissemination activities are considered of primary importance for the EOSCpilot Consortium since only if the achieved results are widely communicated to the public, the impact of the project can be meaningful.

The target groups for the dissemination activities are divided into several equally important categories, including experts and key stakeholders in different communities.

The dissemination activities and all the material developed so far are evenly directed towards all these categories, implementing in every individual case various communication tools and channels.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Dissemination activities are considered of primary importance for the EOSCpilot project Consortium since only if the achieved results are widely communicated to the public, the impact of the project can be meaningful.

The target groups for the dissemination activities are divided into several equally important categories, including experts and key stakeholders in the area of:

- Research-producing Organizations
- E-infrastructures, VREs and other pertinent H2020 projects
- Enterprises
- General public
- National, Regional or Local Government Agencies
- Research Funding Bodies
- Research Infrastructures
- Service Providers
- Learned societies, Research Communities, Scientific and professional Associations
- Academic Institutions and Research Libraries

The dissemination activities and all the material developed so far are evenly directed towards all these categories, implementing in every individual case various communication tools and channels.

1. INTRODUCTION

Dissemination for a project like EOSCpilot is a crucial factor that is pursued through a number of initiatives aiming at informing the communities of the different stakeholders about the project results. The tools that are used, include both on-line and off-line tools and communication supports.

In M6, EOSCpilot defined a detailed Stakeholder identification & engagement strategy plan (D8.2). The deliverable identified the stakeholder groups that EOSCpilot project targets and laid out communication plans for reaching out to these communities. This deliverable (D8.3) provides an overview of the branded dissemination and communication materials created and used at events and online in M1-12.

The following sections provide information on the project branding and logo. Online material is then presented including descriptions of social media accounts and an update on new sections of the website, which provide information on the stakeholder groups and science demonstrators, as well as a number of video interviews published online. Printed material is then described, such as the EOSCpilot project booklet published for the EOSC Stakeholder Forum event (M11), fliers, posters and pop-up banners.

2. DISSEMINATION MATERIAL

2.1. Branding & logo

The first way to “communicate” the project is the identification of the project logo. In EOSCpilot, the logo is represented by a graphic item and a text. Various formats of the logo have been created for use in different contexts (social media, website, printed material).

Figure 1 - Logos

2.2. Website

Since the end of February 2017, the EOSCpilot project has its own official website, available at the following address: <https://eoscpilot.eu/>.

The web site is intended as a dynamic communication tool in the hand of the whole Consortium, that is all partners shall contribute with texts, documents and images to its deployment. The web site is structured in two main sections, public and reserved. The public part represents the “showcase” of the project, and all the institutional information like goals, objectives and news is given.

A full overview of the website is provided in D8.1. Since D8.1, new sections of the website have been added which are in line with the communication plan:

- Who Benefits: providing an overview of the benefits of EOSC to each stakeholder group, how the groups can engage with EOSC and related events.
- Science Demonstrators¹: Description on each of the science demonstrators including those in calls 1 and 2.
- Stakeholder Forum²: New section published to promote the event including overview, registration, agenda, presentations, position papers, venue and accommodation, participant list.
- Governance Forum³: Providing information on WP2 activities including webinars
- External Advisory Board⁴: Profiles of each member

¹ <https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demonstrators>

² <https://eoscpilot.eu/eosc-stakeholder-forum-shaping-future-eosc>

³ <https://eoscpilot.eu/about/governance-framework>

⁴ <https://eoscpilot.eu/about/external-advisory-board>

Figure 2 - Website home page screenshot

2.3. Next steps

With M6-12 a busy period in terms of deliverable submission, M12-14 will see the usage and adaptation of content from these documents and will form the basis of a series of new sections covering critical areas in the project such as policy, governance, interoperability and skills.

2.4. Social media

Social media activities will include active contributions to specific Social Media such as Twitter, LinkedIn and contributions to discussion groups, direct messaging and leveraging current connections within the consortium with the aim of building a loyal support base.

Two branded social media platforms have been set up in M1 and populated: Twitter and LinkedIn.

Figure 3 - EOSC Twitter and LinkedIn accounts

Twitter

Twitter is mainly used to provide brief real-time updates and news, but also as a tool to promote event

activities.

As of writing this document, the EOSCPilot Twitter account has already constructed a solid base of 873 followers fitting several profiles: scientists, researchers, e-infrastructures, consortium partners, policy and regulators, official EC accounts and relevant H2020 projects.

The EOSCPilot Twitter account is in fact intended to reach a broader audience and send out specifically tailored messages to different stakeholders on particular occasions. Indeed, the EOSCPilot Twitter account has been very active in engaging with different stakeholders with more than 500 Tweets sent. We report some examples of Tweets targeting different stakeholders.

Table 1 - Examples of Targeted Tweets

Tweet	Stakeholder Target	Results
	<p>General Public</p>	<p>Total impressions: 3.224</p> <p>Total engagements: 50</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link clicks: 18 • Retweets: 10 • Likes: 6 • Details expand: 7 • Media engagement: 6 • Profile clicks: 3
	<p>Research Institutions & Libraries</p>	<p>Total impressions: 1.620</p> <p>Total engagements: 32</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Link clicks: 20 • Retweets: 7 • Likes: 4 • Hashtag clicks: 1

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is mainly used to bring on board new relevant stakeholders, to send targeted messages and to create and follow discussion groups.

At the time of writing, the EOSCPilot LinkedIn profile has made 244 connections mainly based on EC and EOSC HLEG representatives, e-Infrastructures and VREs representatives, as well as growing number of industry members.

Figure 4 - Example of LinkedIn Post

2.5. Booklet

Published and printed for the EOSC Stakeholder Forum (M11). The booklet is designed to appeal to a multi-stakeholder audience and to give a high-level overview of the EOSC, the different areas that EOSCPilot project is addressing and progress made in M1-11.

Content includes an overview of the key WPs in EOSCPilot project, a summary of each science demonstrator, information on how EOSCPilot project is addressing scientific, technical and cultural challenges, as well as outlines and benefits to each stakeholder group.

Figure 5 - EOSCpilot booklet cover and sample pages

2.6. Posters

A poster was designed and published in M4 and shown at different events. The poster focuses on the FAIR data principles that EOSCpilot adheres to and highlights the EOSC as an open environment for the storage, sharing, analysis and re-use of cross-disciplinary scientific data. The Science Demonstrators are also highlighted on the poster.

Figure 6 - Poster

A second poster targeting the library community was also published and used at the RDA 10th Plenary event (M9). The poster differentiates itself slightly from the previous poster, by highlighting the role of research libraries in the EOSC, what added value they could bring to it and how to engage with the EOSCpilot project to contribute to the EOSC shaping.

Figure 7 - Research libraries poster

2.7. Pop-up banner

The branded project pop up banner provides a general overview of the project and has been used at a series of Y1 events.

Figure 8 – Pop-up banner

2.8. Press Releases

Two press releases have been published in M1-12. The first published in M4 promoting the launch of the

science demonstrators. The second published in M11 focused on the EOSC Stakeholder Forum event.

Figure 9 - Examples of Press Releases

2.9. Newsletters

The EOSCpilot dissemination plan included the regular distribution of a newsletter to inform audiences about the various project activities. These newsletters were available in digital form, through specific web pages as well as email.

A total of eight newsletters have been sent since March 29, 2017. Two kinds of newsletters were sent, namely the EOSCpilot Insider Series, which gives regular updates on all aspects of the EOSCpilot project and coordinates all recipients on the current status of other stakeholders, while EOSCpilot Scoops focus on increasing engagement through events announcements, blogs, reports and surveys.

Figure 10 - Newsletter sample

2.10. Videos

A series of videos have been produced during the EOSCpilot events, aiming to give a high-level overview of some of the issues that emerge throughout the project's lifecycle and discussed during the respective events. The objective is to create such short videos, which stakeholders can watch as targeted messaging and get a quick grasp of the main points of discussion, mainly used as a resource creating content for the EOSCpilot project's social media and website, used for multiple communication, dissemination and engagement activities. Furthermore, often the videos are based on the stakeholders' input right after having participated in sessions of the respective events. Overall, the project's series of videos work as a snapshot that links to more detailed work and keeps up with new developments, highlighting, at the same time, the main challenges the project tackles, as well as future steps.

Table 2 - List of Videos

Title	Description	Link
<u>The Operationalisation of FAIR Principles</u>	A message from Dr. Peter Doorn during the OSFair2017 where he talks about the importance of not just focusing on FAIR principles but also translating them into measurable indicators. He also called for EOSCpilot to present Open Science as not only something theoretical but rather something practical through metrics. Video created by Trust-IT and edited by LIBER Europe	https://youtu.be/wrKuTonastU
Three Key Challenges for the European Open Science Cloud	A message from Dr. Prodromos Tsiavos during the OSFair2017 where he talks about the most significant challenges of Open Science namely, coordination, legislation, and standards and interoperability. Video created and edited by LIBER Europe.	https://youtu.be/xhT-SwsXLZM
Key Message Out of the Policy EOSCpilot Workshop	A message from Dr. Prodromos Tsiavos during the OSFair2017 where he called for the liberalization of data in Europe.	https://youtu.be/3DqQl2WqDII
Towards a Policy Framework for the European Open Science Cloud: The EOSCpilot Perspective	A message from Dr. Prodromos Tsiavos on the side-lines of the OSFair2017 where he outlines the importance of the EOSCpilot workshops. Video created and edited by LIBER Europe.	https://youtu.be/dcagdrPIDF8
Participating in EOSCpilot Workshops: Multi-stakeholder Interaction	A message from Dr. Gintarė Tautkevičienė during the OSFair2017 on the side-lines of the EOSCpilot workshops on the importance of gathering stakeholders together.	https://youtu.be/bqPiWzjqrGE

Participating in EOSCpilot Workshops and the Changing Role of the Library	Dr. Gintarė Tautkevičienė during the OSFair2017 on the side-lines of the EOSCpilot workshops where she stressed the growing importance of libraries for researchers and how crucial it was to have information in libraries not to be limited by geography.	https://youtu.be/eWyyYE0As6Y
A Strong Commitment Towards Open Science	Elena Giglia explained the complexities of EOSC and how a firm commitment is necessary to make Open Science a reality in the EU.	https://youtu.be/65bMkurA0ho
Key Message from the OSFair2017	Elena Giglia stressed the urgency of acting on Open Science to encourage high quality research.	https://youtu.be/e2JS3v-fnnM
Message to a Young Researcher on Open Science	Elena Giglia encourages young researchers to explore the world of Open Science.	https://youtu.be/JR00ffdbccU
Three Main Challenges in Making Data Catalogues FAIR Friendly for EOSC	Prof. Carol Goble and Dr. Keith Jeffery explain the need to expose research metadata of data catalogues, lack of interoperability between EOSC and research data and simplification.	https://youtu.be/IWym08z_joQ
EOSCpilot project and Science Demonstrators (1)	In the video, Dr. Tiziana Ferrari discussed the importance of science demonstrators to the EOSC.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1TTJgY3eEs0
EOSCpilot project and Science Demonstrators (2)	In the video, Matthew Viljoen gave an update on the progress of science demonstrators in the EOSCpilot project. He also discussed the benefits of EOSC to the scientific community.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jingym7d-gPw

<p>EOSC Governance Development Forum Webinars</p>	<p>Videos were produced for the 4th, 5th, 6th and 7th instalments of the series of EOSC Governance Development Forum webinars which are thematic, stakeholder targeted workshops that allow the EOSC governance framework to be elaborated from the stakeholder perspective. The Webinar was facilitated by Matthew Dovey (Jisc), Saara Kontro and Per Oster (CSC)</p>	<p>4th: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ayz9-UO8q1M</p> <p>5th: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wEmxDnEzZTc</p> <p>6th: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3nEnzhE8PZ4</p> <p>7th: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=o-a_XPj5y5M</p>
<p>What is the role of the researcher within the framework of the EOSC</p>	<p>Gareth O’Neil his presentation on skills needed for the EOSC and the role of the researchers within its framework.</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KnEE47Z1qm0</p>
<p>Skills: Building Data Stewardship expertise in Europe</p>	<p>Rahul Thoral on the session “Building Data Stewardship Expertise in Europe: How can we fill the gaps?”.</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8iJVKGPU8pc</p>
<p>The EOSC service architecture and interoperability</p>	<p>Rafael Jimenez & Carole Goble on data interoperability, FAIR data catalogues and data demonstrators.</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ix-esp3SULY</p>
<p>Governance and sustainability of EOSC</p>	<p>Matthew Dovey on the draft governance framework.</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=a42QfIFRwPU</p>
<p>Building a European policy framework</p>	<p>Prodromos Tsiavos on buinding a European policy framework and the policy workshop.</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yv33wC-SzsQ</p>
<p>The EOSC Stakeholder event and soap box session for intermediaries, research communities and libraries</p>	<p>Valentino Cavalli summing up the first day and soap box session for Intermediaries, research communities and research libraries.</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Sp1jy61YkfY</p>
<p>OpenAIRE Advance: a trusted eInfrastructure for the EOSC</p>	<p>Natalia Manola on OpenAIRE Advance, EOSC and further collaboration.</p>	<p>https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=z5TzaCkbmdw</p>

The EOScpilot project – future goals, collaborations and the EOsc Juan Bicarregui on the EOScpilot project’s first year and goals for the future. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oZXOfO33OWM>

Next steps

- General material from the EOsc stakeholder forum to be processed and edited.
- Further videos to be produced during upcoming events

2.11.Champion packs

In an effort to really reach our target stakeholders, we have developed stakeholder-specific material. These include various stakeholder pages on the website and science demonstrators that can show the multiple applications of the EOsc in different scientific contexts.

Stakeholder pages

A section, “Who Benefits” has been dedicated exclusively to stakeholders. Within this section, one page has been committed to each of the stakeholders previously identified.

Each stakeholder page has a detailed description of the respective stakeholder, the benefits of the EOsc for them, as well as the contribution of the EOScpilot project.

The page also contains upcoming events, that could be of interest to that specific stakeholder profile and links to the EOScpilot social media to enable them to keep up to date on the developments of the EOScpilot project.

Table 3 - List of Stakeholder Pages

Title	Link
Research-Producing Organisations, Academic Institutions and Research Libraries	https://eoscpilot.eu/pilots/research-producing-organisation
E-Infrastructures, VREs and H2020 Projects	https://eoscpilot.eu/pilots/e-infrastructures-vres-and-other-pertinent-h2020-projects
Enterprises	https://eoscpilot.eu/pilots/enterprise
General Public	https://eoscpilot.eu/pilots/general-public
National, Regional or Local Government Agencies	https://eoscpilot.eu/pilots/national-regional-or-local-government-agencies
Research Funding Bodies	https://eoscpilot.eu/pilots/research-funding-bodies
Research Infrastructures	https://eoscpilot.eu/pilots/research-infrastructures

Learned Societies, Research Communities, Scientific and Professional Associations	https://eoscpilot.eu/pilots/learned-societies-research-communities-scientific-and-professional-associations
Service Providers	https://eoscpilot.eu/pilots/service-providers

Science demonstrators

A “Science Demonstrators” section has been added to the EOscpilot website. The section is vital for dissemination efforts, as it shows the practical use and benefits of the EOsc across various contexts. At present, 10 science demonstrators are showcased online with a dedicated page for each one of them.

Table 4 - List of Science Demonstrators

Title	Classification	Description	Link
ENVRI	Environmental & Earth Sciences	Radiative Forcing Integration to enable comparable data access across multiple research communities, by working on data integration and harmonised access.	https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/envri-radiative-forcing-integration
WLCG	High Energy Physics	Large-scale, long-term data preservation and re-use of physics data through the deployment of HEP data in the EOsc open to other research communities.	https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/high-energy-physics
TEXTCROWD	Social Sciences	Collaborative semantic enrichment of text-based datasets by developing new software to enable a semantic enrichment of text sources and make it available on the EOsc.	https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/textcrowd
Pan-Cancer Analyses	Life Sciences	Pan-Cancer Analyses & Cloud Computing within the EOsc to accelerate genomic analysis on the EOsc and reuse solutions in other areas (e.g. for cardiovascular & neuro-degenerative diseases).	https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/pan-cancer-analyses-cloud-computing-within-eosc
Photon-Neuron	Physics	The photon-neutron community aims to improve the community’s computing facilities, by creating a virtual platform for all users (e.g., for users with no storage facilities at their home institutes).	https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/photon-neutron-science-demonstrator

PROMINENCE	Energy Research	HPCaaS for Fusion - Access to HPC class nodes for the Fusion Research community through a cloud interface.	https://eoscpilot.eu/prominence-hpcaas-fusion
EPOS/VERCE	Earth Sciences	Virtual Earthquake and Computational Earth Science e-science environment in Europe.	https://eoscpilot.eu/eposverce-virtual-earthquake-and-computational-earth-science-e-science-environment-europe
Life Sciences Datasets	Life Sciences / Genome Research	Leveraging EOSC to offload updating and standardizing life sciences datasets and to improve studies reproducibility, reusability and interoperability.	https://eoscpilot.eu/life-science-datasets
CryoEM Workflows	Life Sciences / Structural Biology	Linking distributed data and data analysis resources as workflows in Structural Biology with Cryo-Electron Microscopy: Interoperability and reuse.	https://eoscpilot.eu/cryoem
LOFAR Data	Physical Sciences / Astronomy	Easy access to LOFAR data and knowledge extraction through Open Science Cloud.	https://eoscpilot.eu/lofar-data

3. DISSEMINATION EVENTS

Events have been profoundly instrumental in disseminating information about the EOsc and engaging with various stakeholders.

Aside from disseminating information through sessions, panels, keynote speeches, event materials and interaction between stakeholders, the events themselves generate press and social media chatter, that extend the communication of EOsc topics outside the events.

Table 5 - List of Dissemination Events

Title	Date	Description
Open Science in Ecological and Evolutionary Research	Dec. 7-8, 2017	The Data Institute (DANS) and the Ecological Institute (NIOO) of the Dutch Academy of Arts and Sciences are committed to open science and have organised, together with the University of Amsterdam, a mini-symposium and various workshops on open science, data and tools in ecological and evolutionary research.
EOsc Stakeholder Forum	Nov. 28-29, 2017	The event aims at charting a course towards a concrete and sustainable EOsc, identifying first steps on the EU added-value of EOsc and its building blocks to make European Open Science a user-friendly reality. During the event, the early results of the EOscpilot project have been communicated, possible EOsc shapes and features have been identified, the practical possibilities of the EOsc have been discussed, the implementation roadmap has been prioritised, governance, funding and business models have been discussed and best practices have been shared.
AEGIS Group/AAI Infrastructure Meeting	E- Nov. 29, 2017	The AARC Engagement Group for Infrastructures (AEGIS) brought together representatives from research and e-infrastructures, operators of AAI services and the AARC project team to bridge communication gaps and make the most of common synergies. This workshop offered an interactive session for researchers and research infrastructures to present their use-cases.
Webinar: A Web-Application to Understand Ecologically Important Seafloor Features in Marine Protected Areas	Nov. 9, 2017	The webinar introduced the PAIM VRE web application, which lets users analyse global data on marine protected areas in relation to essential seafloor features, such as seamounts, canyons, seagrass and mangroves.

EOScpilot/OpenAIRE-DE Joint Workshop "Future Open Science Services for Scientific Communities"	Oct. 24, 2017	This free workshop addressed researchers from diverse scientific communities, as well as research administrators and libraries, to present the EOsc vision, its first phase of implementation via the EOscpilot project, and OpenAIRE's services for Open Science. It took place as a forum for dialogue, serving to collect feedback from participants about their expectations for the EOsc and their views on the challenges and opportunities its implementation will bring. It also aimed to help both EOscpilot and OpenAIRE to shape their future developments according to researchers' needs.
Astronomy & Astroparticle Physics Assets in Building the European Open Science Cloud	Oct. 16-19, 2017	This workshop aimed at building bridges between ESFRI projects, concerned scientific communities, e-infrastructures, industries and further consortia, and to call them to action for the implementation of the EOsc for data interoperability in the astrophysics and astroparticle physics-related disciplines.
EOScpilot Data Interoperability Technical Workshop. Data Catalogues and Datasets in The European Open Science Cloud	Oct. 4-5, 2017	In this workshop, reviewed data models used to describe datasets and data catalogues, as well as requirements of infrastructure services dependent on datasets, have been reviewed. The workshop focused on understanding, testing and evaluating existing technologies to expose and facilitate the integration of dataset metadata.
2nd EOscpilot Governance Development Forum Workshop: Drafting Governance Framework and Principles of Engagement for European Open Science Cloud	Oct. 2-3, 2017	The EOscpilot project has established a Governance Development Forum (EGDF) to enable all different stakeholders to contribute to the development of the EOsc governance framework. The EOscpilot Governance Development Forum (EGDF) is mandated to function and support the establishment of the EOsc. This workshop is part of the forum activities.
RDA Tenth Plenary Meeting	Sept. 19-21, 2017	The 10th RDA Plenary Meeting took place from 19 to 21 September 2017 in Montreal, Canada. The meeting was co-organised by RDA, the University of Montreal and Research Data Canada, Canada.
EOsc Service Provider Workshop	Sept. 13-15, 2017	This event was the first Service Provider Workshop of the EOscpilot project. It brought together Science Demonstrators and Service/Resource Providers, as well as partners from the Service Pilots and Interoperability tasks, in order to facilitate requirements gathering for the EOscpilot project and enable successful delivery to the Science Demonstrators, but also provide input to the EOsc as a whole.

Open Science Fair	Sept. 6-8, 2017	This three-day conference gathered policy makers, funders, publishers and content providers, research infrastructures/communities, researchers, research libraries, institutions and innovators, offering unique insights about e-infrastructures and services, policies as guidance for good practices, research flows and new types of activities (disseminate, mine, review, assess, etc.).
EUDAT And Research Data Management Summer School for Data Scientists	Jul. 3-7, 2017	In collaboration with other pan European e-Infrastructures, this intense training course provided attendees with a better understanding of the European e-Infrastructure landscape, the different tools and services available, and how they can be used to improve the quality of research outputs.
RDA Europe - ENVRI Summer School on Data Management and Data Science	Jun. 12-16, 2017	The 5-day programme included more than 30 different sessions and 15 international data experts. For five days, experienced teachers presented data management and analysis concepts and methods and then support hands-on sessions. The aim was that, by the end of the course, the participants would be able to successfully deal with a wide range of Data Science related activities.
European Open Science Cloud Summit	Jun. 12, 2017	The summit was Europe's moment of commitment to the EOSC and it generated a number of concrete EOSC Statements for implementation.
Working Together Towards a European Open Science Cloud – TNC17	May 29 – Jun. 2, 2017	In the context of TNC17 - the Art of Creative Networking - a dedicated session on the European Open Science Cloud set up a discussion with three exponents of the open data domain and discussed questions such as: What do researchers and research support providers really need and what are the key factors towards the realization of the European Open Science Cloud?
Core Resources for a Data Economy: An ELIXIR Europe Conference	May 11, 2017	The conference's main topic on data resources covered fundamental issues like data preservation, data complexity, interoperability and sustainable data access. The event also collected different stakeholders' perspectives - from funders to infrastructures, academia and industry.
1st EOSCpilot Governance Development Forum Workshop: Research Infrastructures Perspectives on The Governance of European Open Science Cloud	May 9, 2017	The first EGDF workshop was held on 9th May, 2017 in Helsinki, in conjunction with the ERIC RI networking meeting with a focus on research infrastructures aspects and concerns on EOSC and its governance.

<p>EGI Conference 2017 And INDIGO Summit 2017</p>	<p>May 9-12, 2017</p>	<p>The programme focused on the technical roadmap of EGI, with days dedicated to authorisation and authentication, compute services, both HTC and cloud, as well as storage and data services and uptake of the services in scientific communities. Sessions on e-infrastructure governance, procurement and business models were also included in the programme.</p>
<p>EOSCpilot Governance Development Forum 2nd Webinar</p>	<p>May 4, 2017</p>	<p>During the webinar, results from the dedicated stakeholders' survey were discussed and showcased, together with a deep-dive focus on suggested path to carry forward, in view of the EOSC governance framework development.</p>
<p>RDA Ninth Plenary Meeting</p>	<p>Apr. 5-7, 2017</p>	<p>The 9th RDA Plenary Meeting took place from 5th to 7th April 2017 at the Barcelo Sants Hotel, Barcelona, Spain. The plenary meeting was organised by the Barcelona Supercomputing Center-Centro Nacional de Supercomputación (BSC-CNS) with the support of RDA Europe and saw discussions covering the European Data Economy, the European science cloud and more.</p>
<p>Launching the Helix Nebula Science Cloud Prototype Phase - Webcast Event</p>	<p>Apr. 3, 2017</p>	<p>This is a webcast of the awards ceremony for the successful contractors moving to the Prototype Phase of the Helix Nebula Science Cloud Pre-Commercial Procurement taking place at CERN, in Geneva, Switzerland.</p>
<p>BlueBRIDGE Workshop - FAIR Friendly Research Data Catalogues: How Far Are We?</p>	<p>Apr. 3, 2017</p>	<p>The BlueBRIDGE workshop brought together representatives of H2020 projects, e-infrastructures and other European initiatives currently dealing with research data catalogues, to understand how they are approaching the FAIR principles, what status they are at, and to discuss together how to move forward.</p>

Figure 11 - Photos from the EOSC Stakeholder Forum

Some pictures depicting the material distributed during the Stakeholder Forum with the Delegate bag:

Figure 12 - Stakeholder Forum Agenda

Figure 13 - EOSC Stakeholder Forum Flyer (front and back)

Figure 14 - EOsc Stakeholder Forum Banner Graphic

Figure 15 - EOsc Stakeholder Forum signage

4. CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provides an overview of the branded dissemination and communication materials created and used during events and online in the first twelve months of the EOSCpilot (M1-12), with information on the project branding and logo, online material, including descriptions of social media accounts and an update on new sections of the website regarding the information on the stakeholder groups and science demonstrators, as well as a number of video interviews published online. Printed materials are also described, such as the EOSCpilot booklet published for the EOSC Stakeholder Forum event (M11), fliers, posters and pop-up banners.

With M6-12 being a busy period in terms of deliverable submission, M12-14 will see the usage and adaptation of content from these documents to create newly branded communication materials. 2018 will be, in general, the key year for EOSCpilot in terms of taking on board recommendations and discussions from the EOSC Stakeholder Forum event. The governance framework will be elaborated and published while key architectural documents will also be published and interoperability issues addressed. EOSCpilot will also engage with other relevant projects starting in 2018: EOSChub, which will be developing the EOSC services and OpenAIRE Advance, which will continue the development of a pan-European infrastructure for sharing, linking and opening up publications-data-software in a FAIR way.

All these activities will form the basis of a series of new dissemination initiatives covering key areas in the project, such as policy, governance, interoperability and skills, along with the organisation and participation to several events and workshops, like the EOSC Governance workshop at the EUDAT Conference (25 January 2018, Porto) and the EOSCpilot workshops during the International Digital Curation Conference (19-22 February 2018, Barcelona).

The second EOSC stakeholder Forum will be held in M23, November 2018 in Vienna to coincide with other EOSC-related events and the Austrian presidency. This will be the key event in presenting EOSCpilot project's final results. Specific communication strategies and materials will be developed for each event, in order to address the audience in the most effective way, grow the community and engage with all the stakeholders.